

Morphisms among Bosons – 8 Theory

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Abstract:

By analyzing the primorial equation of the coupling constants series, it is possible to reason for the morphisms among bosonic fields, for two reasons, first they are generated by the same element. Second they are all regarded to be net curvature on the manifold, the difference is how much curvature there is, and to solidify the claim that there is no real difference among them.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.11)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

The coupling constants primorial function takes an average of a total curvature pair, and a associate a net curvature number to it by the relative size of the total pairing. That was the procedure used to derive the coupling series back in march 2021. An additional point which should have been mentioned is that since the bosons are regraded to by net curvature on the manifold, which can be described by ripples, the difference between them bosonic ripples is how much curvature there is. The bigger the cluster, the weaker the force. The curvature Is always isomorphic to itself and always generated by the same element, i.e. the majestic (3) proven to be the electron.

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.12)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.13)$$

$$\frac{e^2}{\hbar c} = \frac{1}{128} \quad (1.14)$$

$$\frac{e^2}{\hbar c} \rightarrow \frac{3^2}{128} \rightarrow \frac{8 + (1)}{128} = \frac{1}{128} \quad (1.15)$$

The electron is destabilizing factor over larger and larger clusters of fermions causing net curvatures, or ripples of weaker and weaker magnitude, which means that the curvature ripples are smaller portion of the whole cluster, or that they are covering more and more area over the matrix space which means that the overall curve is flattened. The main point in this short essay is that all bosonic fields are a permutation of the same thing, and the fact that they are generated by the same element toward the same domain is to solidify that claim. Such a theory than makes the description of nature rather simple, curvature is all there is and in bosonic fields it is allowed, and fermion cluster it must vanish.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)